

Animal competition

UG Scholars-Comparison group

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Today is the first day of the forest animal competition.

The lion, the cat and the rabbit are the competitors of the running race. Here is some basic information about them. The lion is the strongest among the three.

The rabbit is the smallest.

The cat is the one who has the most experience of the running race.

After a while the race starts. In the beginning, the rabbit runs faster than the lion and the cat. He is the fastest.

When they get close to the finish line, the situation changes.
The rabbit falls down accidentally.

The lion and the cat come to help the rabbit and they cross the finishing line together.

All of them are the winners.